

BUILDING A GREENER AND FAIRER CLASSROOM: ROLE OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABILITY

Priyanka Naskar

Assistant Professor, Debnarayan Shiksha Sansthan B.Ed. College, Sonarpur,
South 24 Parganas, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Inclusive education is a crucial theme in global society for ensuring equitable access to quality education for all. Now nations are turning towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Specifically SDG 4. SDG4 focuses on providing quality education through inclusion. This study examines the link between inclusive education services and sustainable development at the present situation. The article focuses on the significance of inclusive education in promoting social inclusion, economic empowerment and environmental sustainability. The researcher reviews the role of inclusive education services in promoting sustainable development, exploring key challenges, policies, and practices that contribute to achieving a more inclusive and sustainable world. This research reviews current literature and empirical findings. Tackling obstacles to inclusion while advancing diversity, equity, and social justice in education can greatly aid in creating more inclusive, resilient, and sustainable communities.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Inclusive Education, SDG 4, Social Inclusion, Economic Growth, Equity

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present without jeopardizing the needs of future generations (Dasmohapatra, 2007, P. 28). Sustainable development has a very broad meaning depending on the dimensions being considered. It helps to promote a sustainable world for every generation (Ozili, 2022, 260). It is a process of development that takes into account the environmental, social, and economic dimensions of human activity.” Education is the process of living through a continuous reconstruction of experiences. It is the development of all those capacities in the individual which will enable him to control his environment and fulfill his possibilities (John Dewey)”. Education plays a pivotal role in this process, particularly in achieving social inclusion, economic development, and environmental sustainability. In this context, inclusive education refers to the practice of ensuring that all children, regardless of their abilities or disabilities, have equal access to quality education. “Inclusion in Education is an approach to educating students with special educational needs (Uddin, 2024, 37).” Inclusive education is a set of values, principles and practices that seeks more effective and meaningful education for all students, regardless of whether they have exceptional labels or not (By Giangreco, M. F., 1997). This study explores how inclusive education services contribute to sustainable development and its challenges that arise in the

implementing services. Sustainable development is a holistic approach that aims to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations' to meet them. The concept of sustainable development was first introduced in the 1987 report "Our Common Future," also known as the Brundtland Report. It encompasses economic growth, environmental protection, and social justice, balancing these often competing interests.

Inclusive education is an education system that includes all learners irrespective of their caste, gender and abilities (UNICEF, 2017). Inclusive education is not just about including students with disabilities in the general education classroom. It is about creating a learning environment where all students feel welcomed, respected, and supported. This includes students from all backgrounds, regardless of their race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, or socioeconomic status. The Concept of Inclusive education involves integrating children with special needs, disabilities, and marginalized groups into the mainstream education system (Qian and Rong, 2023). It aims to create learning environments where all students can learn together, regardless of their individual differences. This approach aligns with the values of equity, justice, and respect for diversity, which are essential for sustainable development.

Sustainable Development Goals and Education The United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development outlines 17 goals, with SDG 4 specifically focuses on inclusive and equitable quality education (United Nations). This goal emphasizes ensuring equal access to education for all, promoting lifelong learning opportunities, and reducing discrimination based on gender, disability, and other factors. The United Nations Sustainable Development goals consider the importance of inclusive education in achieving sustainable development by promoting lifelong learning opportunities, promoting social inclusion and empowering marginalized groups. The Mission Statement is "Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all". The intersection of inclusive education and sustainable development is evident in how education systems are change to accommodate diverse learners, fostering social cohesion and economic growth.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyse the role of inclusive education in promoting sustainable values.
2. To explore the pedagogical strategies that integrate inclusivity and sustainability.
3. To access challenges that opportunities in building equitable, Eco- conscious classrooms.
4. To suggest policy and curriculum reforms for holistic sustainability education.

METHOD

This study is based on a qualitative research design and utilizes an analysis of regulatory documents in the fields of inclusive education, sustainable development and current approaches to education. The researcher reviews existing literature, focuses on bridging inclusive education and sustainable development for future. The study considers the problems of incorporating values of inclusion in education. The researcher assesses the influence of inclusive education on sustainable development of society through articles, journals and online based sources.

HISTORY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Inclusive education has evolved significantly since the mid-20th century, driven by civil rights movements that advocated for equal educational opportunities for all children, especially those with disabilities. Initially, students with special needs were often segregated into special schools.

Landmark legislation in the United States, such as the Education for All Handicapped Children Act (1975), mandated free and appropriate public education for children with disabilities. The Salamanca Statement (1994) reaffirmed the right to inclusive education, calling for mainstream schools to accommodate all children regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, or linguistic status. Global commitment emphasized the need for adaptive learning methods and policies. The draft “The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities” (2006) further cemented the commitment to inclusive education as a human right. Today, inclusive education aims to create equitable learning environments that celebrate diversity and meet to individual needs.

INTEGRATION OF SUSTAINABILITY AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Naukkarinen and Jouhkimo (2021) in their study discussed about the collaboration between schools and universities to promote integrated and inclusive education for sustainability. This study revealed the need for integrated approaches to address the interrelated challenges of social justice and environmental sustainability in the Anthropocene Era (Leach, et.al., 2018). Sustainable development has three important interdependent components (Dasmohapatra, 2007, P.28).

Social Sustainability

Social sustainability highlights equitable wealth distribution and community well-being, which can foster economic growth by creating a healthy workforce and fostering innovation.

Economical Sustainability

Economic sustainability depends on natural resources for production and services; thus, it must consider environmental impacts to ensure long-term viability.

Environmental Sustainability

Environmental sustainability is essential for maintaining the ecosystems that support human life and economic activity, highlighting the need for responsible resource management.

Together, these pillars form a holistic framework where the failure of one can undermine the others, requiring a balanced approach to achieve true sustainability

Inclusive Education and Social Sustainability

Inclusive education approach fosters a resilient and inclusive community. Inclusive education is crucial for maintaining social sustainability and inclusive community. This approach promotes equality, social justice, and the empowerment of marginalised groups. Schools implementing

inclusive practices help their stakeholders break down barriers to participation, giving all children the opportunity to contribute to society. By meeting the needs of all learners, inclusive education creates a more just and equitable society, reduces inequality and promotes sustainable social development.

Inclusive Education and Economic Sustainability

The economic aspect of sustainable development emphasizes the generation of wealth as well as its fair distribution. Inclusive education initiatives play a pivotal role in promoting economic sustainability by equipping every student, including those with disabilities, for significant engagement in the job market. By providing individuals with essential employment skills, inclusive education serves to diminish poverty, enhance economic self-sufficiency, and foster community economic growth. Ultimately, inclusive education cultivates a labor market that is more accessible, enabling individuals of all abilities to both contribute to and gain from the economic system.

Inclusive Education and Environmental Sustainability

Inclusive education contributes significantly to environmental sustainability by increasing equitable access to education for all, including marginalized groups. It promotes social inclusion, which is vital for building resilient communities capable of addressing environmental challenges. Education raises awareness of climate issues and equips students with skills to adapt to environmental change, thus contributing to Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) and other SDGs. Inclusive education empowers people with disabilities to participate in sustainability efforts, ensuring diverse perspectives in climate action.

CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Despite the importance of inclusive education for sustainable development, several challenges hinder its effective implementation

Lack of Resources and assistive devices

Many schools lack the financial, human, and material resources needed to accommodate diverse students.

Limited access to Education

Rigid, test based curricula and Inaccessible school environments for learners.

Teacher Training

Inadequate teacher preparation and professional development prevents teachers from effectively teaching in inclusive classrooms. Limited teacher training and support for students with diverse learning needs.

Cultural and Societal Attitude

Social stigma and discrimination against children with disabilities or marginalized groups creates barriers to inclusion.

Policy Gaps

Although many countries have policies promoting inclusive education, gaps in implementation and monitoring often lead to inconsistent practices.

Case Studies of Inclusive Education Services and Their Impact on Sustainable Development

Several countries have implemented successful inclusive education models that contribute to sustainable development. For Example:

Finland

Finland's inclusive education model prominences equity, personalized learning, and collaborative learning. This approach has donated to higher education outcomes and social cohesion in the country.

India

India has made significant progress in inclusive education through the implementation of the Right to Education (RTE) Act. The law mandates free and compulsory education for all children, including those with disabilities, which has had a positive impact on reducing educational inequality. As India's approach to inclusive education evolves, the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 aims to transform the country through equitable and inclusive education (NGIFEIE). The goal is to ensure that all students, especially those with diverse learning needs, can thrive in an inclusive environment with equal opportunities.

South Africa

In South Africa, the Inclusive Education White Paper 6 aims to transform the education system by removing barriers to learning and creating an inclusive school environment. This policy has helped improve access to education for students from marginalized communities. case study provides an insight into the implementation status of inclusive education across South Africa. It was introduced in 2001 to establish a system where learners with disabilities can learn close-by their peers with appropriate supports(Inclusive Education in Action case studies,2019).

POLICY RECOMENDETIIONS

Chakraborty, S., Yerramilli, S., and Kumar, P., (2022). explores the policies and frameworks for sustainability in inclusive education pointed at dispensing equitable education opportunities for differently-abled students, highlighting the importance of sustainable and inclusive educational practices.

To ensure that inclusive education services effectively contribute to sustainable development, the following recommendations are proposed:

Inclusive Curriculum Design

1. The developing and implementing curriculum includes sustainability concepts across all subjects.

2. Ensure that the curriculum is inclusive of diverse learning needs and backgrounds accessible to students.

Increased Investment in Education

Governments and international organizations need to allocate more resources to support inclusive education services, including infrastructure development and teacher training. Invest in inclusive education technology.

Capacity Building for Educators

Ongoing professional development for equipping teachers with the necessary skills to work in inclusive classrooms is essential. Therefore, teacher training programs should be organised by government authorities to sustain inclusive education environment.

Community Engagement

Changing societal attitudes towards inclusive education through creating awareness and community participation and advocacy are pivotal for overcoming cultural barriers. Educators should connect classroom learning with real world sustainability challenges through community project.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Governments should implement vigorous monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to evaluate the impact of inclusive education policies and practices on sustainable development.

DISCUSSIONS:

We have explored the difficulties associated with putting inclusive education into practice for sustainable development along with relevant policy suggestions. It is important to understand that inclusive education is structured uniquely. A key point to remember is that flexibility is a fundamental characteristic of inclusive education. We should consider what is necessary to create a suitable inclusive environment for sustainability and how educators can assist diverse learners.

Educators have to create an inclusive classroom that supports global sustainability. Students will show high levels of collaborative behaviour and remain empathic toward diverse learners. Educators should build strategies that prepare learners to address the global challenges. Here, how to build a welcoming classroom environment for students where they feel comfortable, equal and supported in sustainability. To promote diversity and equality in classroom, educators celebrate cultural differences, break stereotypes, and use regional languages.

Educators should apply universal Design for Learning in classroom environment. Universal Design ensures that all students can actively participate and access learning. Foster collaborative learning methods is essential for learning, using group work, project based learning to encourage students, problem- solving skills, which are essential for addressing sustainability issues.

An inclusive classroom uses technology for accessibility in learning. Adaptive technology and materials support students with disabilities and diverse learners. An inclusive classroom

for global sustainability not only supports academic achievement for all students but also cultivates social inclusion, economic empowerment, and environmental consciousness—essential for building resilient and sustainable societies

After our discussion, we can say that inclusion is a societal concept. When students participate in group work, and project based learning with diverse learners, they feel encouraged and more comfortable. Researchers experiences in their studies, showed that students exhibited a reduction in fear of diverse learners and simplification of interactions with them (Fayzrakhmaniva, 2014).

CONCLUSION

Inclusive education services are not only a matter of social justice but also a key driver of sustainable development. The traditional focus of many schools has been to develop around standardized educational programs rather than to accommodate individual needs. By ensuring that all children, regardless of ability or background, have access to quality education, we can build a more equitable, inclusive, and economically viable society. However, successful realisations of this study are the challenges identified in inclusive education for sustainability. The intersection of inclusive education and sustainable development emphasizes the need for policies and practices that promote social inclusion, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. In case study, this research finds that India can provide efforts to overcome the problems of the education system and contribute to empowering the integration of inclusive education for sustainable development.

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